

The untapped potential of neglected roots and tubers for the development of ingredients with application in food industries

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Abstract

Underground storage organs as roots and tubers (R&T) have represented one of the main sources of energy for human survival since ancient times as has been proved by archaeological findings. To ensure safety and palatability of underground storage vegetables, processing was needed, giving rise to different transforming techniques that are related not only to cooking being born but also to human brain remodeling and modern society foundations. As subsistence crops even in our time for rural communities, R&T are valued in many cultures, but diet uniformization has decreased their biological diversity all over the globe, where edible landscapes are being modified to feed growing populations. Few potatoes, sweet potatoes and cassava varieties have led the food industry development among the most common monocrops but, depending on the geographic coordinates, many other genetic resources of R&T may be used as raw materials for food applications. Such is the case of aroids, yams, and other minor crops that also contain bioactive compounds and micronutrients that in joint with different genotypes of the aforementioned monocrops, account for a vast array of possibilities. Some examples of the components that might be extracted from various R&T include starch, a well-known ingredient from many industries even outside food uses, and fiber or pigments that have attracted the attention for nutraceutical developments, since recent findings highlight the benefits of these kinds of substances for human health. Multidisciplinary approaches are called to action for the use of these food matrices that have an effect beyond the commodity markets, as promoters of an agrobiodiverse landscape that faces sustainability challenges in current agricultural models, while depicting a wide display of unfulfilled options in the food research field of R&T based ingredients.

Keywords: underground vegetables, tuber processing, food ingredients, agrobiodiversity, underutilized species.

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